

Confluence of Leadership to Professional Development and Teacher's Performance: Basis for Management Strategies

Roda L. Watiwat
Mindoro State University
lamonteroda19@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study determined the relationship between the extent of leadership of school heads and the level of professional development and teachers' performance as a foundation for management strategies. This study used descriptive-correlational and comparative methods of research. The participants of the study were the 10 school heads and 121 senior high school teachers from selected schools of the Schools Division of Oriental Mindoro. A self-made questionnaire was utilized. The study revealed that while both teachers and school heads rated school leadership and professional development at high levels, school heads consistently rated themselves and the programs more favorably than teachers did, indicating a perceptual gap. Nearly all senior high school teachers were rated as outstanding, yet the absence of a significant correlation between leadership and performance

suggests other factors may influence evaluation outcomes. Notably, leadership practices such as decision-making, delegation, and communication showed strong positive relationships with aspects of teachers' professional development, emphasizing leadership's critical role in fostering growth and collaboration. However, there were no significant differences in how leadership practices were perceived across different indicators, while variations in perceptions of professional development were significant among teachers but not among school heads. These findings informed the formulation of targeted management strategies aimed at aligning leadership actions with meaningful professional development, enhancing instructional effectiveness, and addressing the specific needs and growth areas of senior high school educators.

Keywords: *Leadership practices, professional development, teachers' performance, management strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Globally, the problem when it comes to leadership is the gap between what the school heads think the teachers need and what these teachers actually need. This misunderstanding leads to wasted intervention efforts and low motivation as teachers feel that they are not being heard (Zhang et.al (2022). Many studies pointed out the importance of collaborative leadership in addressing this problem.

Zhao and Xia (2022) that allowing the teachers to have autonomy brings out engagement. When they are allowed to have voice and participate in decision-making they contribute more to better learning outcomes.

Just the same, Zhang et al (2022) revealed that a good instructional leadership enhance teacher to be more innovative. When school heads fail to hear their teachers' inputs, there seems to be discrepancy in goals and strategies that hinder the institution's goal.

On the other hand, when it comes to professional development, the trainings offered are not relevant to the actual needs of the teachers on the field. They remain generic and meant to fit all without specifically tailoring them to the specific contexts of the learning that is taking place. Also, there are not enough follow ups after trainings and workshops. It is not monitored if the new skills are applied, hence teachers revert back to their old method, wasting the chance for improvement.

To support this, Darling-Hammond et al. (2020) pointed out that a relevant professional development is continuous and content-focused for it to make a difference in classroom instruction. However, up to this day, teachers attend workshops and then forget about the skills learned, having no support in applying them to their actual classroom. Hence, it has no impact to the classroom instruction and learners' outcome.

In the Philippine educational system, the problem in jiving the leadership concerns and professional development is very notable (Garcia, 2021). It had been always the school heads struggle to implement management plans that caters to the needs of their teachers, especially in their professional development and performance (Cruz and Santiago, 2021). Their busy schedule makes it impossible for them to sit down and really plan the professional development suited for every teacher that they handle. Furthermore, with little training in educational leadership, some school leaders find it challenging to design a functional management plan to suitable diverse teacher needs, which, combined with potential resistance to change, further complicates the effective implementation of these plans. This challenge can lead to low performance which may affect learning outcomes.

The identified research gap is the absence of evident link between leadership practices, professional development, and their influence on teaching performance. Many previous studies address these areas separately in a broader context. However, this study will address the missing link by assessing how leadership influences teachers' professional development and performance in an integrated, evidence-based way.

DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2016, emphasizes the need for school heads to effectively manage and support teachers through well-defined strategies and practices. This order highlights the importance of aligning leadership with performance management systems to enhance teaching quality and student learning. In this study, the development of comprehensive management strategies that integrates leadership, professional development, and performance will be guided by this DepEd order.

In Schools Division of Oriental Mindoro, pre survey revealed how significant are the issues on leadership and effectiveness of professional development and teacher's performance. The difficulty of the school heads in creating management plans that address the diverse needs of their teachers is believed to affect educational outcomes. It was observed that IPPD and SPPD are prepared hastily. This manner of preparing these important documents results to less targeted, less effective strategies for teacher growth and development. When this happens, it can lead to misaligned objectives, limiting the impact of these efforts to the overall outcomes.

The need for a well-understood link between leadership style, PD and teaching effectiveness is the gap addressed by this study. Although studies pointed out the importance of joint leadership practices and professional for better learning outcomes, there are only few research that converted their findings into actual management plans designed for specific settings such as SDO Oriental Mindoro.

This study bridged the gap by examining the specific interactions between leadership, professional development, and teacher's performance within the district, aiming to produce coherent management strategies that aligns these elements. This approach could help standardize quality teaching practices, improve student outcomes, and create actionable insights for other divisions facing similar challenges.

METHODOLOGY

This research employed a descriptive-correlational and comparative method of research. The procedures involved the use of self-made questionnaire to assess the leadership, professional development strategies and teaching performance.

Ten (10) school heads and one hundred twenty-one (121) proficient senior high school teachers are the respondents of the study from selected schools of the Schools Division of Oriental Mindoro. For school heads total enumeration method was utilized. For SHS teachers proportional random sampling was used.

A researcher-made questionnaire was the main instrument of this study. The researcher used DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2016 for leadership and PPST, 2016 as reference for professional development. The questionnaire has three parts: leadership, professional development strategies and teaching performance.

To make sure the research tool is effective, two district supervisor and two school head examined and evaluated the researcher-made questionnaire to confirm its validity. Furthermore, the researcher utilized single test reliability. The test was administered to 10 non-respondents and was analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha.

Moreover, the study utilized descriptive statistics such as mean and rank and frequency and percentage to describe the results of the study. Moreover, inferential statistics such as Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Scheffe's Test were employed. Results and Discussions

1. Extent of Leadership of School Heads

Extent of Leadership of School Heads

Statement	Teachers			School Heads		
	Mean	Rank	Verbal Description	Mean	Rank	Verbal Description
1. Decision Making Process	4.12	4	High Extent	4.77	2	Very high Extent
2. Communication Approach.	4.17	2	High Extent	4.75	3	Very high Extent
3. Delegation of Tasks	4.14	3	High Extent	4.66	4	Very high Extent
4. Conflict Resolution Methods	4.07	5	High Extent	4.60	5	Very high Extent
5. Vision and Goal Setting	4.27	1		4.85	1	
Overall mean	4.15		High Extent	4.73		Very high Extent

The extent of leadership of school heads as assessed by teachers and school head themselves yielded an overall mean of 4.15 for teachers (high) and 4.73 for school heads (very high). Teachers rate their principals' leadership as consistently high, while principals see their own performance as very high.

2. Level of Professional Development of SHS Teachers

Level of Professional Development of SHS Teachers

Statement	Teachers			School Heads		
	Mean	Rank	Verbal Description	Mean	Rank	Verbal Description
1. Philosophy of teaching	4.18	5	High Extent	4.51	2	Very high Extent
2. Dignity of teaching as a profession.	4.43	1	High Extent	4.50	3	Very high Extent
3. Professional links with colleagues	4.37	2	High Extent	4.40	5	High Extent
4. Professional reflection and learning to improve practice	4.27	3	High Extent	4.44	4	High Extent
5. Professional development goals	4.21	4	High Extent	4.54	1	Very high Extent
Overall mean	4.31		High Extent	4.48		High Extent

For the level of professional development of SHS teachers as assessed by teachers and school heads an overall mean of 4.31 (high) for teachers and 4.48 (high) for school heads is obtained. Both teachers and school heads view professional development at a high level, but school heads consistently rate it slightly higher—especially in teaching philosophy and professional dignity.

3. Level of Teacher's Performance

Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Adjectival Rating
4.500-5.000	108	89%	Outstanding
3.500-4.499	13	11%	Very Satisfactory
2.500-3.499	0	0	Satisfactory
1.500-2.499	0	0	Unsatisfactory
below 1.499	0	0	Poor

Total	121	100%
Mean : 4.61		Outstanding

Out of 121 Senior High School (SHS) teachers, 108 or 89% received an outstanding rating, while 13 or 11% got a very satisfactory rating. No teacher received ratings under satisfactory, unsatisfactory, or poor. Nearly all SHS teachers are rated outstanding, indicating consistently exceptional performance.

4. Relationship between the Extent of Leadership of School Heads and the Level of Professional Development of SHS Teachers

Correlational analysis between the extent of leadership of schoolheads and level of professional development of SHS Teachers of the respondents

IV: Extent of Leadership of School Heads	DV: Level of Professional Development of SHS Teachers									
	Philosophy of Teaching		Dignity of Teaching as a Profession		Professional Links with Colleagues		Professional Reflection and Learning to Improve Practice		Professional Development Goals	
	T	SH	T	SH	T	SH	T	SH	T	SH
	r-value		r-value		r-value		r-value		r-value	
Decision-making Process	0.586*	0.109 ⁿ _s	0.543*	0.518*	0.476*	0.269*	0.589*	0.053 ⁿ _s	0.543*	0.032 ⁿ _s
Communication Approach	0.562*	0.192*	0.521*	0.335*	0.396*	0.473*	0.539*	0.023 ⁿ _s	0.479*	0.168 ⁿ _s
Delegation of Tasks	0.673*	0.257*	0.595*	0.399*	0.508*	0.027 ^{ns}	0.647*	0.085 ⁿ _s	0.583*	0.162 ⁿ _s
Conflict Resolution Methods	0.704*	0.141 ⁿ _s	0.611*	0.252*	0.493*	0.387*	0.629*	0.171 ⁿ _s	0.604*	0.271*
Vision and Goal Setting	0.655*	0.077 ⁿ _s	0.519*	0.062 ⁿ _s	0.422*	0.114 ⁿ _s	0.654*	0.120 ⁿ _s	0.632*	0.196*

df = 120 Critical r-value = 0.174 ns = not significant * = significant T= Teachers
SH=School head

The data revealed that school leadership practices significantly impact various aspects of teachers' professional development, with notable correlations such as decision-making showing strong relationships with teachers' philosophy of teaching ($r = 0.586$), professional links with colleagues ($r = 0.543$), and professional development goals ($r = 0.543$). Delegation of tasks also demonstrated high correlations with professional links ($r = 0.647$), reflective practice ($r = 0.629$), and development goals ($r = 0.583$). Communication approach was positively correlated with

philosophy of teaching ($r = 0.562$) and professional links ($r = 0.521$). These implies that inclusive and communicative leadership effectively supports teachers' growth, collaboration, and goal setting.

5. Relationship between the Extent of Leadership of School Heads and the Level of Teachers' Performance

Correlational Analysis between the Extent of Leadership of School Heads and Level of Teacher's Performance

IV: Extent of Leadership of School Heads	Critical r-value	IV: Teacher's Performance Computed r-value	Results
Decision-making Process	0.174	0.060	Not significant
Communication Approach	0.174	0.067	Not significant
Delegation of Tasks	0.174	0.140	Not significant
Conflict Resolution Methods	0.174	0.010	Not significant
Vision and Goal Setting	0.174	0.046	Not significant

df=120

The results reveal that there is no significant correlation between the leadership practices of school heads and the level of teacher's performance levels, based on the computed r-values for all leadership indicators ranging from 0.010 to 0.067 being lower than the critical r-value of 0.174 t 0.05 level of significance.

6. Difference in the Extent of Leadership of School Heads across its Indicators

One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the extent of leadership of school heads across indicators as perceived by teachers

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	F-Value	Critical Value at $\alpha = 0.05$	Result
Between Groups	2.62	4	0.656	1.31	2.37	Not Significant
Within Groups	299.50	600	0.499			
Total	302.12	604				

The F-value is 1.31, which is compared with the critical value of 2.37 at a significance level of 0.05. Since the F-value (1.31) is lower than the critical value (2.37), the result is considered not significant. This means that there is no significant difference in the extent of leadership of school heads across the different indicators as perceived by teachers.

One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the extent of leadership of school heads across indicators as perceived by school heads

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	F-Value	Critical Value at $\alpha = 0.05$	Result
Between Groups	0.381	4	0.095	0.475	2.58	Not Significant
Within Groups	4.80	45	0.107			
Total	5.5.181	49				

Meanwhile, for the school heads, the F-value is 0.475, which is compared with the critical value of 2.58 at a significance level of 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). Since the F-value (0.475) is lower than the critical value (2.58), the result is not significant. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the extent to which school heads perceive their leadership practices across the different indicators.

7. Difference in the Level of Professional Development of SHS Teachers across its Indicators

One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the level of professional development of SHS teachers across indicators as perceived by teachers

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	F-Value	Critical Value at $\alpha = 0.05$	Result
Between Groups	5.47	4	1.37	3.74	2.39	Significant
Within Groups	219.60	600	0.366			
Total	225.07	604				

The F-value is 3.74, which is compared with the critical value of 2.39 at a significance level of 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). Since the F-value (3.74) is greater than the critical value (2.39), the result is significant. This indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in the teachers' perceptions of their professional development across the different indicators.

**One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the level of professional
development of SHS teachers across indicators as perceived by school
heads**

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	F-Value	Critical Value at $\alpha = 0.05$	Result
Between Groups	0.215	4	0.054	0.306	2.58	Not Significant
Within Groups	7.91	45	0.176			
Total	8.125	49				

Meanwhile, for school heads, the F-value is 0.306, which is lower than the critical value of 2.58 at $\alpha = 0.05$, leading to the conclusion that the differences between indicators are not significant.

8. Proposed Management Strategies

The results from the analysis indicate that there is no significant difference in the perception of professional development among Senior High School (SHS) teachers across various indicators, as perceived by both teachers and school heads. This suggests that while teachers' professional development is seen as important in all areas, there may be opportunities to enhance the focus on specific aspects or introduce more targeted strategies to further improve their growth. Moreover, the uniform perception of professional development across indicators implies the need for a balanced and inclusive approach to teacher development. Based on these findings, it is crucial to implement strategies that address the diverse aspects of teachers' professional needs while ensuring alignment with the school's vision for continuous improvement.

For the implementation of the proposed management strategies, a structured system will be established at the school level to ensure consistency and clarity across all initiatives. Monthly teacher consultation meetings and feedback sessions will be conducted to encourage open communication and immediate resolution of staff concerns. Classroom observations, performance data, and survey tools will be used to gather insights on the impact of administrative decisions. Weekly task reviews with department heads and task owners will ensure that delegated responsibilities remain aligned with the school improvement plan. Conflict resolution will be systematized using a standardized logbook and reporting forms. Culturally responsive teaching practices will be reinforced through INSET sessions, where teachers will receive training on integrating students' cultural contexts into their lesson plans. To promote professionalism, biannual refresher courses will be implemented, with emphasis on communication protocols. Monthly Professional Learning Community (PLC) sessions will foster collaboration and shared instructional planning among teachers. Teachers will also be encouraged to complete quarterly self-assessment rubrics and reflection journals to enhance reflective teaching practices.

For the monitoring and evaluation, school heads and department coordinators will be responsible for consolidating monthly reports on academic performance and feedback from stakeholders to assess the effectiveness of school-wide decisions. Documentation from weekly task reviews will be analyzed to determine alignment with strategic goals. Records from the conflict resolution logbook will be reviewed regularly to ensure that resolutions are documented and followed through consistently. Evaluation of cultural

inclusivity will be done by checking lesson plans and conducting periodic classroom walkthroughs. Spot checks and observation protocols will be used to assess professionalism in teacher-parent and teacher-student interactions. Attendance and contributions to PLC meetings will be tracked to measure the level of collaboration. Teacher self-assessment rubrics and reflection journals will be reviewed quarterly by supervisors, who will provide coaching and support based on the findings. These monitoring tools will not only gauge the implementation's success but also inform future adjustments to enhance school management and instructional leadership.

Conclusion

The conclusions drawn from the study highlight several key insights. A noticeable gap exists between how teachers and school heads perceive leadership practices, indicating the need for clearer communication and shared understanding of effective leadership. School heads' slightly higher ratings of professional development suggest that training programs should be more closely aligned with the actual needs of teachers. Although most teachers received outstanding ratings, this points to the importance of refining evaluation tools to better capture both strengths and areas for improvement. The study confirms that leadership significantly influences professional development, underscoring its role in fostering growth and collaboration. However, the lack of a significant link between leadership and performance ratings suggests that other variables also impact teacher evaluations. With no major differences in leadership practices across indicators, school heads are encouraged to maintain a balanced and consistent approach. Teachers' varied perceptions of professional development further emphasize the need for more targeted and responsive programs. Ultimately, the proposed management strategies aim to bridge these gaps by aligning leadership efforts with purposeful professional development, thereby enhancing the overall quality of teaching and learning.

In view of the foregoing findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are drawn: School principals may hold quarterly leadership review meetings with department heads and teacher representatives to openly discuss feedback on decision-making, communication, delegation, conflict resolution, and goal-setting, and to agree on one key area to improve before the next review. Academic coordinators may conduct quick post-training surveys among SHS teachers after every in-service session to identify content gaps, then plan follow-up sessions that target the most requested topics like differentiated instruction or assessment tools. Performance review committees may enhance the SHS teacher evaluation process by including an individual growth plan section, requiring teachers to set one measurable improvement goal per semester and reflect on progress during the year-end review. School heads may integrate short peer practice-sharing segments in monthly SHS department meetings, where one or two teachers briefly demonstrate a new strategy or tool that worked in their subject area (e.g., project-based learning in HUMSS or STEM). School heads may complement teacher performance ratings by including informal classroom observation notes and brief student feedback forms to provide a fuller picture of instructional effectiveness beyond administrative input. Senior High School leaders may use a rotating leadership focus calendar (e.g., January for improving task delegation, February for enhancing communication) to ensure balanced development across all leadership areas throughout the school year. Master teachers or department chairs may create small, subject-aligned professional learning communities (PLCs)—like "Teaching Reading in English for Academic and Professional Purposes" or "Innovations in TVL Instruction"—meeting twice a month for peer feedback and lesson sharing. School improvement teams may pilot the proposed management strategies in selected SHS strands (e.g., STEM and ABM), collect teacher input on their effectiveness, and adjust the approach before expanding school-wide.

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